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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15072299>

FEATURES OF MEASLES IN CHILDREN AT THE PRESENT STAGE

Abstract:

Measles is an acute, highly contagious infectious disease caused by a virus that most often affects children. The main symptoms are fever, runny nose, cough, conjunctivitis, and a characteristic erythematous maculopapular rash. Complications such as pneumonia, acute otitis media, and encephalitis may also occur. Measles is transmitted by airborne droplets or through direct contact with secretions from the nose, mouth, and throat of infected individuals. Measles outbreaks can occur in populations where less than 10% of people are immune to the measles virus. Measles vaccination is a reliable method of preventing infection.

Keywords: *measles, children, vaccination, rash, pneumonia, clinical case.*

Introduction. Measles infection is caused by a single-stranded, RNA-negative respiratory virus of the Paramyxoviridae family and the Morbillivirus genus [1].

Measles virus is a highly contagious pathogen that causes an acute infectious disease accompanied by a characteristic spotted-papular rash [1,2].

The World Health Organisation (WHO) estimates that approximately 777,000 people died in 2000 due to measles complications [3].

Measles is transmitted by airborne droplets or through direct contact with the nasal, oral and throat secretions of infected individuals. Outbreaks can occur in populations where less than 10% of people are immune to the measles virus [1].

The incubation period for measles infection is 7 to 21 days, with most people showing symptoms 10 to 12 days after infection. The diagnosis is based on complaints, an epidemiological history (measles vaccination, contact with measles patients or travel), and a physical examination of the child.

Measles usually presents as an acute respiratory viral illness that usually lasts 2-4 days. The clinical picture includes fever, malaise, anorexia, cough, runny nose and conjunctivitis. Koplik spots, which are pathognomonic for measles, appear in the first days of illness. They are bluish-white, slightly raised, erythematous lesions on the mucous membrane of the cheek, usually opposite the first molar. Koplik spots usually disappear in a few days. Discrete erythematous spots appear on the face and neck one day after the appearance of Koplik spots. This rash becomes more confluent when it spreads to the entire body. It usually lasts from 3 to 7 days, then disappears in a similar pattern. Measles is characterised by the confluent nature of this rash and its spread from the face and neck to the whole body. Patients are highly contagious from 4 days before the rash appears to 4 days after [4].

Measles can cause numerous organ-specific complications that can lead to hospitalisation and even

death, including gastrointestinal disorders, neurological, pulmonary, ophthalmological, haematological, renal and dermatological complications [5].

Complications of measles:

Pneumonia - either primary measles pneumonia or secondary viral or bacterial pneumonia - is the most common cause of death in measles infection. The viruses that complicate measles are usually adenovirus and herpes simplex virus. The bacteria that cause secondary infection are usually *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* [4,6].

Laryngotracheobronchitis (croup) is the second most common cause of death. The pathogens are similar to those that cause measles pneumonia.

Otitis media is the most common complication of measles [4].

Acute measles encephalitis occurs in 1 case of measles per 1000 and leads to permanent brain damage. During the convalescent phase of the disease, fever reappears with the development of headache, seizures and impaired consciousness [4,6].

Encephalitis with measles corpuscles is the result of infection of the brain with the measles virus in individuals with impaired cellular immunity [6].

Subacute sclerosing panencephalitis is a rare, fatal degenerative disease of the central nervous system caused by persistent infection with a defective measles virus. The exact pathophysiology is unknown, but it is believed that mutations in the viral genome lead to changes in cellular immunity. The disease usually occurs 7-10 years after the initial measles infection, especially in those who contracted measles before the age of 2 years. Clinical manifestations include behavioural disorders, intellectual impairment, and myoclonic seizures that slowly progress to a vegetative state [4,6].

Measles is a highly transmissible disease, and vaccination coverage of at least 95% is required to maintain herd immunity [7].

In 2009-2014, complications were observed in 9% of cases, most commonly diarrhoea (38%), pneumonia

(33%), dehydration (25%), otitis media (16%), thrombocytopenia (10%), encephalitis (3%), pancytopenia (1%) and hepatitis (1%).

In the United States, due to a highly successful public health campaign based on universal vaccination, measles was officially declared eradicated (i.e. no endemic transmission for ≥ 12 months) in 2000. However, in recent years, the United States has seen a resurgence of measles outbreaks, largely driven by travel-related contacts and low community vaccination rates.

The global annual incidence of measles in 2000 was 14.5 per 100,000 people, but thanks to the rapid roll-out of immunisation programmes around the world, the annual incidence has fallen from 83% to 25% [5].

In 2017, there were 109,000 projected measles deaths worldwide, compared to 545,000 measles deaths in 2000. It is estimated that from 2000 to 2017, immunisation programmes prevented an estimated 21.1 million deaths worldwide [8].

In 2018, the number of measles cases worldwide increased by 167% compared to 2016.

In 2019, there was a decline in vaccination coverage due to an anti-vaccination campaign, which led to a measles outbreak [7].

During 2018 and 2019, there was an increase in the number of reported measles cases in countries such as the United States of America, Madagascar, Ukraine, India

Due to vaccination, measles has been modified. Modified measles is a mild form of measles with a longer incubation period of 17 to 21 days. Also, this variant of measles is not very contagious.

Symptoms such as headache and fever appear within 7-14 days of exposure to inactivated measles vaccine and may indicate the onset of atypical measles. Unlike typical measles infection, atypical measles is associated with a rash that first appears on the limbs and then spreads to the trunk. Atypical measles is severe but not highly contagious [8].

Materials and methods: We conducted a literature review based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 10 years. We analysed information on the incidence of measles among children and the characteristics of measles at the present stage.

Objective: to analyse the literature, research and identify current changes in measles incidence, complications of measles and possible atypical courses of measles.

Results and discussion: We present our own clinical case of measles with pneumonia:

Boy M., 7 years old, was admitted on 30.01.2025 to the Chernivtsi Regional Children's Clinical Hospital to the infectious diseases department No. 2 with complaints of fever up to 39.2°C, cough, runny nose, redness of the eye, skin rash and single vomiting due to cough.

From the medical history, it is known that he fell ill on 25.01.2025 with the onset of cough, redness of the eye, nasal congestion. The first rash on the face, neck and trunk appeared 4 days later. He was treated on his own, and when his condition deteriorated, an emergency medical team was called, which sent him to the

Regional Children's Clinical Hospital, from where he was hospitalised in the infectious diseases department No. 2. From the medical history, it is known that the child was born at 34-35 weeks of gestational age. After birth, he was in intensive care for congenital pneumonia, intrauterine infection, and osteomyelitis. It is also known that there were frequent colds. No vaccinations other than BCG were carried out.

The condition on admission is closer to severe, due to respiratory failure, respiratory symptoms, otitis media, excoriation and a spotted-papular rash on the face, trunk and extremities, sometimes with a draining and haemorrhagic component. Fever up to febrile levels. According to the results of laboratory tests dated 30.01.2025: Complete blood count: leukocytes - $3.2 \cdot 10^9/l$, rods - 20%, segmented - 20%, eosinophils - 2%, lymphocytes - 56%, monocytes - 2%, ESR - 8 mm/h; detection of immunoglobulin class M to measles virus dated 17.02.2025 - positive result.

According to instrumental methods of examination - chest radiography of 30.01.2025: signs of bilateral bronchopneumonia. Consultations of related specialists: ophthalmologist - subacute conjunctivitis, ENT: acute pharyngitis, acute otitis media, pulmonologist: outpatient bilateral viral and bacterial pneumonia, acute course. Respiratory failure of the first and second degree.

During hospitalisation, the following treatment was provided: third-generation cephalosporins (9 days), eye drops, inhalation with saline, oral rehydration therapy, infusion therapy (0.9% NaCl, 5% glucose), glucocorticosteroids (4 days), vitamin A, antipyretics.

As a result of the treatment, the patient's condition improved. His breathing is clear, there are no breath sounds, the rash has disappeared, and his body temperature has returned to normal. The child was discharged from the hospital in a satisfactory condition.

Conclusion: Measles is an acute, highly contagious, viral disease accompanied by inflammatory changes in the upper respiratory tract and a characteristic rash. Measles is transmitted by airborne droplets or through direct contact with nasal, oral and throat secretions of infected people. Measles also has many complications, the most common of which are pneumonia, laryngotracheobronchitis, and acute otitis media; less common are nervous system complications such as measles encephalitis and subacute sclerosing panencephalitis. The only method of prevention is vaccination.

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